

Knowledge and Practice of Specialists and Residents of Gynecology towards the Management of Post- Menopausal Burning Mouth Syndrome

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ABSTRACT

Objective: To assess the knowledge of gynecologists about burning mouth syndrome among post-menopausal women and to assess the treatment modalities used by gynecologists for Burning mouth syndrome among post-menopausal women.

Study design: Cross sectional, Descriptive, Questionnaire based study.

Place and Duration of Study: Data collection for this study conducted in four teaching and practicing hospitals of Lahore (CMH Lahore, Jinnah Hospital, FMH and Ghurki trust teaching hospital) from July 2017 to November 2017.

Methods: A questionnaire was filled by specialists and 3rd and 4th year resident gynecologists in four teaching and practicing hospitals of Lahore from July 2017 to November 2017. The inclusion criteria was both genders of any age, teaching and practicing hospitals. The exclusion criteria included: private clinics, medical officers. Data was analyzed using SPSS version 23 (IBM SPSS Statistics, version 23, USA). Chi square test was used to compare frequencies amongst groups. A p value of <0.05 was set as the level for statistical significance.

Results: A total of 43 out of the 50 gynecologists including specialists and residents responded to questionnaire. 18.3 % residents and specialists said that they knew about burning mouth syndrome.

Conclusion: The results yielded that only 2.3% of the physicians thought that the condition should be referred to a dentist for the treatment. 11.6% thought that no treatment is required, 9.3% thought only counselling was required and medications were the mode of treatment for 7.0%.

Keywords: *Burning Mouth Syndrome, Post-menopausal women, burning sensation*

INTRODUCTION

Menopause, also known as the climacteric, is the time in most women's lives when menstrual periods stop permanently, and they are no longer able to bear children.¹ Menopause typically occurs between 49 and 52 years of age.² Some of the common symptoms include hot flashes, night sweats, difficulty sleeping, reduced libido, vaginal dryness and pain, headaches, mood changes, palpitations, joint stiffness, reduced muscle mass, recurrent urinary tract infections (UTIs) and increased risk of developing certain other problems, such as weak bones (osteoporosis).³ Among oro-dental problems, gingival bleeding, receding gums, loose teeth, and burning sensation in oral mucosa are some common problems in menopausal women.⁴

A study carried out in Jodhpur Dental College showed clinical manifestations such as mucosal burning/pain (25.8%), breath change (6.3%), facial pain (3.6%) and dry mouth (27.1%) among post menopausal women.⁵ Burning mouth syndrome (BMS) is a burning sensation in the mouth with no underlying dental or medical cause. No signs of disease are found in the mouth.⁶ Burning mouth syndrome is an oral pain disorder with a prevalence of 5–18%. In a study done on Finnish people, the aim was to assess the burning mouth syndrome in the

general population. Altogether 431 subjects (237 females, 194 males) participated in the study. 15% of the subjects had experienced prolonged oral burning but a half of them had some clinically observable oral mucosal lesion or oral candidiasis. The prevalence of the complaint was significantly higher in females than in males.⁷ Oral complaints and salivary flow were surveyed in 669 men and 758 women randomly selected from 48,500 individuals between the ages 20 and 69 years. Fifty-three individuals (3.7%), 11 men (1.6%) and 42 women (5.5%), were classified as having BMS. In women, no BMS was found in the youngest age group, but in the age group 30 to 39 years the prevalence was 0.6% and increased to 12.2% in the oldest age group.⁸ About 18-33 % of the women of the post-menopausal phase complaint of burning mouth syndrome.⁹

This study was conducted to assess the knowledge and management of practicing Gynecologists in teaching hospitals of Lahore about burning mouth syndrome in post-menopausal women with its high prevalence among women.

METHODOLOGY

The study was carried out as a descriptive cross sectional survey of specialists and residents of gynecology. Ethical review was sought from the ethical review board of the Institute of Dentistry, CMH Lahore Medical College. A questionnaire was designed and piloted on 10 medical house officers of the institute. The questionnaire

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was modified and filled by specialists and 3rd and 4th year resident gynecologists in four teaching and practicing hospitals of Lahore from July 2017 to November 2017. The inclusion criteria was both genders of any age, teaching and practicing in hospitals. The exclusion criteria included private clinics and medical officers. The short questionnaire was collected on same day, or one week later.

Data was analyzed using SPSS version 23 (IBM SPSS Statistics, version 23, USA).

Chi square test was used to compare frequencies amongst groups. A p value of <0.05 was set as the level for statistical significance.

RESULTS

A total of 43 doctors responded to the survey. These included a total of 26 residents (60.5%), 14 consultants (32.6%) and 3 registrars (7%). The year of graduation ranged from 1985-2014.

When asked about the appearance of BMS in the oral cavity, 19 residents, 2 registrars and 6 consultants did not answer this question. 10 (23.3%) of the doctors said that

the oral cavity appeared normal. 3 (7%) consultants thought that the lesion appeared as “other” type of lesion in the oral cavity. Another 3 (7%) of the doctors thought BMS appears like a red lesion in the oral cavity as described in fig 2.

An interesting aspect to this research was the management of this condition. The doctors were given an option of counselling, medications, no treatment and referral to a dentist. 69.8% did not answer this question, while 11.6% didn't think these patients required any treatment. 9.3% said patients with this condition should be counselled and about 7% said they should be prescribed medication. However, only 2.3% thought that this is a dental condition and that it should be referred to a dentist.

The doctors were then asked if any, what medications they used for this condition? 86% did not answer this question, while 7% said mouthwashes should be administered. 2.3% of them thought that oral rinses should be administered and 2.3% thought that topical creams should be prescribed.

Figure 1: Knowledge of post-menopausal BMS

Table 1: Knowledge of post –menopausal women among different designations

do you know about postmenopausal BMS?	Count	Designation			Total
		resident	registrar	consultant	
No	22	3	10	35	
Yes	4	0	4	8	
Total	26	3	14	43	

Figure 2: Appearance of BMS in the oral cavity

Figure 3: Management of BMS

Figure 4: Medications used for BMS

DISCUSSION

Burning mouth syndrome is a common condition in post-menopausal women as Misra *et al.* reported nearly 21% of 105 postmenopausal Indian women having BMS; a fairly high prevalence.¹⁰ Various diseases/clinical entities like lichen planus, candidiasis, viral infections, xerostomia etc., also have a characteristic symptom of burning sensation, but in burning mouth syndrome, pain is accompanied without any alteration in oral mucosa. International Association for the Study of Pain defined burning mouth syndrome (BMS) as a burning pain in the tongue and/or other oral mucous membrane in an absence of clinical signs or laboratory findings.¹¹ The term burning mouth syndrome should only be used when a definite cause has not been found.¹² Scala A *et al* suggested two clinical forms of BMS. Primary BMS/essential/idiopathic BMS, for which organic local/systemic causes cannot be identified and secondary BMS resulting from local/systemic pathological conditions and thus this form responds well to the

etiology-directed therapy.¹³

In 1994, Lamey, *et al.* classified the syndrome into 3 types: Type 1 (35%), defined by daily pain where symptoms are absent upon awakening but gradually increase in severity as the day progresses, unrelated to psychiatric conditions. Type 2 (55%) is defined by constant pain present during day and night; these patients are very anxious. Type 3 (10%) is defined by intermittent pain, with pain-free intervals, occurring in non-usual sites such as the floor of mouth and the posterior oropharynx; in this type, there is a relation between pain and the type of food taken as well as allergens.¹⁴ Unfortunately, keeping in mind the fact that the condition is fairly prevalent, the specialists have failed to identify it. Besides that they are not entirely sure where these patients should be referred to for treatment and almost only 2% of the specialists from our research thought that it should be referred to a dentist. Basker RM found in a study that the frequency of BMS is 26% amongst patients attending a menopause clinic, 10% diabetic and 2.6%

general dental clinics.¹⁵

Ashortcoming in this research was the varying opinion among Physicians that whether this problem should be catered by gynecologist or medical specialist. The debate was regardless the patient presents to the outpatient departments of either clinics, who were the entitled specialists to treat this condition. This caused a lot of setback in our research.

A major drawback we encountered during a study was that the questionnaires were left unanswered after answering the first question as they didn't have any idea about burning mouth syndrome in post menopausal women.

CONCLUSION

The knowledge and prevalence of Burning Mouth Syndrome among the residents and specialists of gynecology was not significant with respect to the research done in various hospitals. This needs to be addressed by the teaching bodies of our country and the knowledge should be included in the curriculum.

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